

Spectrophotometric Study of the Colour Reaction Between Thorium Ions and Galangin

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Galangin (3,5,7-trihydroxyflavone) forms an intense yellow-coloured complex with thorium ions. The colour reaction has been investigated for spectrophotometric determination of thorium. The complex shows maximum absorption at 410 m μ at pH 2.2. The region of maximum absorption shifts slightly towards the higher wave lengths with increase in pH and at pH 4.2, occurs at 420 m μ . The system obeys Beer's law over the pH range 2.2 to 4.2 and the method can be satisfactorily used for spectrophotometric determination of small quantities of thorium. Molar composition of the complex, as determined by Job's and slope-ratio methods, has been found to be 1:1.

Some of the organic reagents, which have been used for colorimetric estimation of thorium, are morin¹, quinalizarin², naphthazarin³, and morellin⁴. The authors⁵ have used 5,7-dihydroxyflavone, i.e., chrysin, for the spectrophotometric determination of thorium. The use of galangin (3,5,7-trihydroxyflavone) has already been made for determination of uranium⁶ by spectrophotometric method. It has now been found that galangin can similarly be used for determination of thorium. The reagent gives an intense yellow-coloured complex with thorium, the characteristics of which have been studied spectrophotometrically. All the investigations have been carried out in 50% ethanol medium. Beer's law is obeyed from 4 to 16 p.p.m. of thorium concentration. The molar ratio of thorium to galangin in the complex is 1:1.

The reagent possesses the advantage of forming a very stable complex with thorium. This intense yellow-coloured complex is soluble in aqueous ethanol and thus differs from the complexes formed by some other well-known reagents which are insoluble and form lakes. High intensity of colour makes it possible to determine conveniently even traces of thorium.

EXPERIMENTAL

The flavone was obtained from the ether extract of the plant rhizomes of *Alpinia officinarum* Hance. Thorium nitrate (A.R., B.D.H.) was used for preparing standard solutions ($M/1,000$). Thorium content was determined gravimetrically by precipitating with oxine. An ethanolic solution of galangin containing 0.270 g./litre ($M/1,000$) was prepared.

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The absorption spectrum of the flavone was taken with a Hilger UV spectrophotometer. All other spectrophotometric observations were taken in a Coleman spectrophotometer, model No. 14. All pH measurements were made with the help of a Metrohm pH-meter, type E-350.

Absorption Spectra.—The absorption spectrum of galangin was taken in 95% EtOH. Maximum absorption was observed at 270 $m\mu$ and 360 $m\mu$. Thorium-galangin complex,

FIG. 1. Absorp. spectra of Th-galangin complex at diff. pHs.

however, has its maximum absorption at 410 $m\mu$ at pH 2.2. The value shifts from 410 $m\mu$ to 420 $m\mu$ with the increase in pH from 2.2 to 4.2. A slight shift in the absorption maximum is shown by the curves in Fig. 1. Wave lengths 410 $m\mu$ and 420 $m\mu$ were therefore chosen in the investigations that follow. The molar ratio of the flavone to thorium was maintained at 5 while preparing the solutions for the spectra. One ml of thorium nitrate solution ($M/1,000$) was mixed with 5 ml of the flavone solution ($M/1,000$) and the mixture was finally diluted to 25.0 ml, maintaining 50% alcoholic medium. These conditions were kept constant in subsequent studies.

Effect of Acidity.—The effect of acidity of the complex was studied and it was found that below pH 2.2 there was no significant coloration of the complex and beyond pH 4.2, light precipitation started on keeping the solutions for some time. The flavone solution itself was found to become sufficiently yellow beyond pH 4.2. Combination of thorium ions with hydroxyl ions and subsequent precipitation of thorium hydroxide may be the reason of turbidity beyond pH 4.2. The pH of the solutions was adjusted by addition of a very dilute solution of HCl or NaOH.

Stability of the Complex.—The intense yellow-coloured complex was found to be quite stable and no change in colour was observed even on keeping it for 40 hours in 50% EtOH medium between pH 2.2 and 4.2.

FIG. 2. Adherence to Beer's law.

Beer's law.—The complex obeys Beer's law from 4 to 16 p.p.m. of thorium concentration. The results obtained at pH 3.45 are summarised in Fig. 2.

Interference due to Diverse Ions.—The effect of oxalate, citrate, borate, tartrate, zirconyl, titanium, and copper ions were tested on the thorium complex and these were found to interfere even if present to the extent of 20 p.p.m. in the solution of the complex containing about 10 p.p.m. of thorium.

Molar Composition of the Complex.—Method of continued variation⁷⁻⁹ was employed for determining the composition of the complex. Optical densities of a series of solutions

Thorium soln. (ml).

FIG. 3. Job's method.

x ml of Th soln. ($M/10,000$) mixed with $(5-x)$ ml of galangin soln. ($M/1,000$). x varied from 1 to 4. Total vol. = 25 ml in 50% EtOH medium.

prepared by mixing x ml of $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ thorium solution with $(5-x)$ ml of $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ galangin solution (where x was varied from 1 to 4), keeping 50% ethanolic medium and finally diluting to 25.0 ml, were determined at 410 m μ , 420 m μ , and 430 m μ , employing galangin solution of the corresponding strength as reference solution. The peak in the curve (Fig. 3) occurs when the molar ratio of thorium to galangin is 1:1.

The slope-ratio method⁹ was also used for determining the composition of the complex. Parallel curves were obtained showing that the composition of the complex as 1:1.

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